

DETERMINATION OF RADIONUCLIDES AND WAYS TO REDUCE THEIR IMPACT ON THE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *This article presents the results of a study to determine the radionuclides of the uranium decay chain in samples of uranium production and ways to reduce their impact on the environment, namely the values of the specific activity of radionuclides ^{234}U , ^{230}Th , ^{226}Ra , ^{222}Rn , ^{218}Bi , ^{214}Po , etc. taken from uranium waste tailings, off-balance uranium ore dumps and underground uranium leaching sites.*

Keywords: *uranium facility, radiation factors, radioecological problems, uranium production, value of specific activity, radionuclides of the uranium decay chain technogenic uranium facility, uranium waste tailings, off-balance uranium ore dumps, depleted areas of underground uranium leaching, technological solutions, exhaust gases, nitrous oxides uranium.*

Introduction. Among the general radioecological problems associated with the development of uranium production, it especially determines the values of the specific activity of radionuclides ^{234}U , ^{230}Th , ^{226}Ra , ^{222}Rn , ^{218}Bi , ^{214}Po and other uranium decay chains in samples taken from the territories of operating uranium processing plants and their man-made objects [1 -5]. The main technogenic sources of environmental pollution at these facilities are uranium dump tailings, dumps of off-balance uranium ores, spent areas of underground uranium leaching, technological solutions, exhaust gases from the uranium oxide calcination shop, etc. [6-8].

On the basis of the above, the study and determination of the states of man-made objects of uranium production, the specific activities of radionuclides - ^{234}U , ^{230}Th , ^{226}Ra , ^{222}Rn , ^{218}Bi , ^{214}Po and other uranium decay chains in samples of uranium dumps taken from the tailing dump, dumps of off-balance uranium ores, spent areas of underground leaching uranium, process solutions and into exhaust gases from the uranium oxide calcination shop and the issuance of practical recommendations for reducing the impact of these radionuclides on the environment is an urgent task of analytical chemistry, applied nuclear physics and radioecology [9-10].

The goals and objectives of the study were to solve the following:

- study of methodological and metrological characteristics of radiochemical, nuclear-chemical and instrumental radiation analysis of the states of natural and man-made objects of uranium production;

- improvement and implementation of radiometric methods for determining the specific activities of radionuclides to determine the radiation impact of a man-made uranium object on the environment;

- based on the determination of the specific activity of radionuclides of chemical elements - ^{234}U , ^{230}Th , ^{226}Ra , ^{222}Rn , ^{218}Bi , ^{214}Po and other uranium decay chains in samples of uranium dumps taken from the tailing dump, dumps of off-balance uranium ores, spent areas of underground leaching of uranium, technological solutions and waste gases from the uranium oxide

As can be seen from the results obtained, given in tab. 1, the concentration of most chemical elements such as - Al, Fe, Ti, Ca and S in the process of leaching decreases by half in the spent samples (1*, 2*, 3*) than in the original samples (1, 2, 3) . And the concentration of most chemical elements such as - K, Mn, Sr, etc. do not change during the leaching process. Their concentration remains the same as they were in the original samples. The SiO₂ concentration changes only slightly.

Table 1

Results of semi-quantitative analysis of some chemical elements in soil contaminated with radionuclides in initial samples and samples after treatment

Elements	Concentration in initial samples, (%)			Concentration after treatment, (%)		
	1	2	3	1*	2*	3*
Al	3,4	3,2	3,0	2,0	2,0	1,8
Fe	2,3	2,6	2,8	1,6	1,8	1,6
Ti	0,31	0,28	0,29	0,13	0,11	0,14
Ca	0,98	0,81	0,92	0,64	0,61	0,58
S	0,65	0,58	0,71	0,40	0,38	0,43
K	2,3	2,1	2,4	2,4	2,3	2,1
Mn	0,042	0,047	0,040	0,044	0,045	0,042
Sr	0,014	0,018	0,013	0,012	0,014	0,011
Zn	0,013	0,019	0,014	-	-	-
V	0,012	0,016	0,013	-	-	-
Cr	0,012	0,021	0,018	-	-	-
SiO ₂	73,2	74,1	70,9	68,8	69,4	69,1

In Table 2 shows the results of measuring DER, specific activity of radionuclides - ²³⁴U, ²³⁰Th, ²²⁶Ra, ²¹⁸Bi, ²¹⁴Po of the uranium decay chain in contaminated soils of underground uranium leaching sites.

As can be seen from the tab. 2 the value of the exposure dose rate of gamma cure - EDR of selected soils is directly proportional to the specific activity - radionuclides - ²³⁴U, ²³⁰Th, ²²⁶Ra, ²¹⁸Bi, ²¹⁴Po of the uranium decay chain and there is the same dependence on the specific activity of the radionuclide - Ra²²⁶, since this radionuclide is the main gamma emitter in the uranium decay chain.

During acid underground leaching, the vast majority of radium (99.3-99.6%) does not dissolve and remains with solid ore residue in the bowels of the Earth during underground leaching. A little more radium is dissolved in the process of carbonate leaching (up to 1.5-2.2%). In this case, the concentration - ²²⁶Ra and ²³⁰Th in waste solutions reaches the following values: ²²⁶Ra - 35 * 10⁻⁶ μKu / ml; ²³⁰Th- 22 * 10⁻⁶ μCu / ml, which is 10 times higher than the maximum allowable standards for discharge into open water bodies (for both isotopes).

Table 2

Results of measurement of DER, specific activity of radionuclides - ²³⁴U, ²³⁰Th, ²²⁶Ra, ²¹⁸Bi and ²¹⁴Po

№ уро̄б	DER , (mkR/h)	Soil specific activity , (Bk/kg)				
		²³⁴ U	Ra ²²⁶	Th ²³⁰	²¹⁸ Bi	²¹⁴ Po

1	15,1-23,4	473	705	8	7	8
2	14,9-27,2	603	417	25	5	7
3	13,5-20,8	460	270	19	6	9
4	13,6-20,1	509	243	25	5	7
5	12,4-28,3	445	406	17	7	7
6	12,0-21,3	529	169	22	5	8
7	11,9-20,1	563	110	29	6	9
8	11,1-19,3-	558	57	22	7	10
9	343,1-840,1	2282	21020	288	5	8
10	298,2-610,7	2200	13010	183	5	8
11	271,4-312,5	1932	8609	161	6	6
12	261,7-332,0	369	8756	25	5	7
13	15,1-23,4	273	829	6	6	6
14	25,8-89,3	105	1534	4	7	9
15	33,5-68,8	343	1348	15	5	8
16	25,0-91,0	180	1492	6	6	6
17	44,2-60,6	562	1249	19	5	9
18	37,1-72,3	384	1504	16	6	6
19	25,0-65,1	383	1088	17	6	6
20	47,7-60,6	323	1173	6	4	10

The values of the specific activity of radionuclides - ^{234}U , ^{230}Th , ^{226}Ra , ^{218}Bi , ^{214}Po varies in a wide range, that is, for the radionuclide - ^{234}U - from 105 Bq / kg to 2282 Bq / kg, for the radionuclide - ^{230}Th - from 4 Bq / kg to 288 Bq / kg, for the radionuclide - ^{226}Ra - from 57 Bq / kg to 21020 Bq / kg, for the radionuclide - ^{218}Bi , from 4 Bq / kg to 7 Bq / kg. and for the radionuclide - ^{214}Po from 6.0 Bq/kg to 10 Bq/kg.

Conclusion Thus, the main pollutants of the region were identified as radionuclides - ^{234}U , ^{230}Th , ^{226}Ra , ^{218}Bi , ^{214}Po present in samples of off-balance dumps, areas of underground uranium leaching and uranium waste tailings. To improve the radioecological state in this region, it is recommended to process off-balance uranium ores by geotechnological methods (vat or heap leaching), carry out reclamation work and cover the places where spent uranium wastes are deposited - with gold-bearing ores processing waste or fertile soil.

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